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Power-to-X activities at Haldor Topsoe: our approach for electrification of the chemicals industry

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Abstract

Haldor Topsoe considers electrolysis and solid oxide electrolysis cells (SOEC) in particular an enabling technology for the electrification of the chemical industry. Here, we present status updates on our various stepping stone projects, CO₂ electrolysis for CO production and H₂O electrolysis for biogas upgrading, as well as the demonstration project for the electrification of ammonia production.

Compared to other electrolysis technologies, SOEC allows for the conversion of CO₂ into useful chemicals at very high efficiencies and at a faradaic yield of 100%. Haldor Topsoe is commercializing the CO₂ electrolysis technology as eCOs™: a platform for on-site on-demand CO generation from CO₂ feedstock for customers requiring a reliable and safe feed of carbon monoxide at a scale of up to thousands of Nm³ CO/h.

The use of SOEC for the production of H₂ is also interesting, not merely due to the inherently high conversion efficiencies that can be achieved, but also due to system-level synergies found in integrating the endothermal electrolysis process with an exothermal chemical synthesis process. The pilot plant for upgrading CO₂ in biogas into pipeline quality synthetic natural gas (SNG), located at Foulum, Denmark, provides an example of such integration.

Haldor Topsoe is a market leader in providing technological solutions and catalysts for the production of ammonia. Since 2000, Topsoe has commissioned >60 ammonia plants across the world with an accumulated capacity of almost 100 000 metric tonnes of NH₃ per day. It is Haldor Topsoe's ambition to become a technology provider for future fully electrified ammonia plants. A novel process is being developed where the nitrogen for the ammonia synthesis is provided by burning air between the SOEC stacks and utilizing steam generated in the Haber-Bosch loop as feedstock. This results in very efficient plant (71 % LHV efficiency) and eliminates investment in an air separation unit.

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Introduction

Carbon dioxide emissions from industrial sources account for approximately 20% of global energy-related CO₂ emissions (production of cement – 7%, iron and steel – 6%, chemicals – 5%, aluminium – 1%) [1]. Along with heavy transport and aviation, industry is a relatively challenging sector to decarbonize, but efforts to electrify industrial processes and to replace fossil fuels with climate-friendly alternatives (e.g. hydrogen, carbon monoxide or syngas produced via electrolysis) are intensifying. In the European Union, these efforts are supported by a strong political will [2].

Electrolysis is an enabling technology for de-coupling the production of industrial chemicals from the use of fossil fuels and therefore plays a central role in various Power-to-X scenarios. Here, X can be hydrogen, carbon monoxide, syngas, methanol, ammonia or any other chemical or fuel [3]. When electrolyzers are powered by renewable electricity, then the CO₂ emissions associated with the production of X will be minimal and may even be negative.

Currently, the majority of water electrolysis systems used for Power-to-X applications are based on alkaline electrolyzers [4]. However, while alkaline electrolysis is a mature technology, the conversion efficiency of alkaline cells remains low: electric power consumption on stack level is typically higher than 4.6 kWh/Nm³ H₂ [4]. In large-scale Power-to-X plants, the levelized cost of product is to a large extent determined by the price of electricity and the electric power consumption of the electrolysis units [5]. Alternative electrolysis technologies, and SOEC in particular, are attractive due to the higher conversion efficiencies. For example, H₂ production at 3.1 kWh/Nm³ H₂ on stack level has recently been demonstrated using SOECs [6]).

Here, we provide status updates on our various stepping stone projects towards large-scale Power-to-X projects: i) CO₂ electrolysis for CO production, ii) H₂O electrolysis for biogas upgrading, and iii) electrification of ammonia production.

1. CO₂ electrolysis for CO production

Haldor Topsoe is offering world's first commercial CO₂ electrolysis system based on SOEC technology [7]. The system, called the eCOs™ Plant, combines CO₂ electrolysis and gas purification in one unit and is capable of producing 96 Nm³ high-purity carbon monoxide gas per hour. An eCOs™ Plant is a stand-alone unit with power, CO₂, and product gas connections (Fig. 1) that allows the customer to produce carbon monoxide on-site and on-demand from carbon dioxide feedstock. The eCOs™ technology can be used to produce CO a scale of up to thousands of Nm³ CO/h.

On-site CO generation using the eCOs™ technology has several important advantages compared to common alternatives, such as CO supply by tube-trailers or gas cylinders. First, CO is produced on-site from unhazardous CO₂ feedstock, which is safe to store and handle. Secondly, CO can be produced on-demand only when needed, reducing or eliminating the need for storing large amounts of CO on-site. This significantly reduces the safety risks associated with handling and transportation of carbon monoxide. Thirdly, there is no inertia in the system, as CO production can be stopped instantaneously by cutting off the supply of power to the SOEC unit. An eCOs™ plant provides the customers with intimate control over their CO production, ensures security of supply, and drastically reduces costs for storage, rentals and connections. Finally, the unit is capable of supplying highly pure CO gas at an economically attractive price.

Figure 1. An eCOsTM Plant capable of producing 96 Nm³ CO/h. The plant is built up of six modules: electrolysis unit, gas supply unit, compressor unit, gas purification unit, cooling water unit, and control unit (the control unit is not shown).

Two eCOsTM plants are scheduled to be commissioned in Ohio, USA, later this year. The 96 Nm³ CO/h plant will have a modular design, and will consist of an electrolysis unit, a gas supply unit, a compressor unit, a gas purification unit, a cooling water unit, and a control unit (Fig. 1). Electrolysis, compressor, gas supply and control units will be housed in standard 40-foot containers for easier shipping and installation. The electrolysis unit will include 6 coreboxes, each with 8 TSP-1 stacks. These 96 Nm³ CO/h plants will be the first commercial (subsidy-free) SOEC plants in the world.

TSP-1 stacks can successfully be operated in dry CO₂ electrolysis for extended periods of time. Fig. 2 shows the results of a system test with a TSP stack in a corebox operated at 750°C and at a current of -70 A, which corresponds to a production rate of 2.2 Nm³ CO/h. The stack has been operated for almost 14 000 hours, during which it has produced more than 30 000 Nm³ (35.5 tonnes) of CO. Despite being subjected to 21 thermal cycles, the degradation rate for the stack remained low: the average cell voltage increased at a rate of 7.9 mV kh⁻¹, when calculated over the entire test period, and 9.2 mV kh⁻¹, when calculated over the last 4 000 hours. On average, the stack consumed 3.44 kWh electric power for producing 1 Nm³ CO.

Faradaic efficiency (FE) is a metric that is often used to describe the selectivity of electrochemical processes. In the context of CO₂ electrolysis for CO production, FE is defined as the fraction of total electrolysis current that is used towards reducing CO₂ to CO [8]. Obtaining FE efficiencies close to unity is non-trivial in low-temperature (aqueous) CO₂ electrolysis systems, where the CO₂ reduction reaction competes with the hydrogen evolution reaction and with other side-reactions, such as the production of hydrocarbons or oxygenates [8,9]. In SOEC systems operating in dry CO₂ electrolysis, FE values of 100% are relatively easy to obtain due to the fact that no water species is present in the feed gas. The FE values recorded during the 14 000-hour stack test are plotted in Fig. 3. Faradaic efficiency, determined using gas chromatography measurements on product gas,

remained between 99% and 100% throughout the test (there were issues with the calibration of the gas chromatograph during the first part of the test). The uncertainty of the FE estimates is expected to be around +/- 1%, i.e. the slight differences in FE values observed in Fig. 3 are likely due to the measurement uncertainty and not fluctuations in stack FE.

Figure 2. A system test of a TSP-1 stack in dry CO₂ electrolysis. The SOEC current was fixed at -70 A and the inlet temperature at 750°C. The stack was subjected to 21 thermal cycles (indicated by white circles) and several load cycles.

Figure 3. Faradaic efficiency towards CO production in the system test shown in Fig. 2, verified using gas chromatography measurements of the product gas. The gas chromatograph calibration was off during the first four measurements.

2. H₂O electrolysis for biogas upgrading

Biogas produced by anaerobic digestion consists typically of methane and carbon dioxide in a volumetric ratio of approximately 6:4, as well as several thousand parts per million of various sulfur compounds (mainly H₂S) [5,6]. One way to upgrade the value of biogas is to mix it with hydrogen produced via steam electrolysis in a methanation reactor to produce synthetic natural gas (SNG). SOEC technology offers unique benefits in connection with biogas upgrading, because the heat released by the exothermal methanation step can be used to generate steam for high-temperature electrolysis, thus avoiding evaporation of water by electricity. Coupled with the favorable thermodynamics and kinetics at elevated temperatures, this increases the overall efficiency from electric power to additional methane product significantly.

In “EI-upgraded biogas”, a project funded by the Danish Energy Agency (EUDP), a 10 Nm³/h SNG demonstration plant based on SOEC, biogas desulphurization and catalytic methanation was designed, built and operated for more than 2100 hours. Very high energy conversion efficiency (H₂ production at 3.07 - 3.09 kWh/Nm³), rapid load-following capability, and better than pipeline-quality SNG production was demonstrated [6].

A follow-up project “EI-upgraded biogas II”, also funded by EUDP, aims to bring the technology readiness level from TRL 6 to TRL 8. The goal is to operate the demonstration plant for at least 4000 hours including transient operation to adapt to the anticipated future electricity market. During the 4000 hours the hydrogen production should be 16 Nm³/h (corresponding to 10 Nm³/h upgraded biogas starting with a raw gas with 40 % CO₂) with stack temperatures not exceeding 780 °C. Additionally, a more cost-effective sulfur removal unit using enriched air from SOEC will be introduced [10], preventive maintenance on balance-of-plant components will be carried out, and a steam clean-up step will be incorporated. The project partners include Haldor Topsoe and Aalborg University.

3. Electrification of NH₃ production

Ammonia (NH₃) is a commodity chemical with a global production capacity of around 180 million tonnes per year [11]. Ammonia is mainly used as a fertilizer but is also being seriously considered as a potential carbon-free fuel for the maritime industry. In order to replace 30% of the current marine fuel consumption with NH₃, an additional 150 million tonnes of ammonia would need to be produced [12]. Today, ammonia is almost exclusively generated from a feed gas of hydrogen and nitrogen, obtained via steam reforming of natural gas (Fig. 4A). Aided by better catalysts, improved process integration and the economies of scale, the average energy consumption of ammonia plants has been decreasing steadily over the past decades from over 60 GJ/tonne NH₃ in 1955 to 36.6 GJ/tonne NH₃ in 2008. The best-in-class NH₃ plants operate at ~28 GJ/tonne NH₃ [13]. Improved energy efficiency can be directly translated into a decrease in greenhouse gas emissions (on a tonne per tonne basis). However, even if it were possible to produce ammonia at the thermodynamic limit of 20 GJ/tonne NH₃, the resulting CO₂ emissions would still be substantial, making traditional pathways of ammonia production incompatible with future fossil- and CO₂-free energy scenarios.

Previously, ammonia plants using hydrogen produced by alkaline electrolyzers were common (Fig. 4B), and recently, in the light of increased concerns about CO₂ emissions and constantly decreasing renewable electricity prices, this technology is again gaining interest [14]. If the electricity required for running the electrolyzers and the air separation unit (ASUs) originates from renewable energy sources, then NH₃ can be produced with a low carbon footprint. However, the energy intensity of alkaline electrolyzers is high (> 4.6

kWh / kg H₂), which means that the energy consumption of such plants (>36 GJ/tonne NH₃ [11]) will be higher than for modern conventional plants.

If alkaline electrolyzers were replaced with SOECs as shown in Fig. 4C, the efficiency of the NH₃ plant could be increased considerably. Assuming the electrolysis cells are operated at the thermoneutral voltage of 1.29 V, the energy consumption of such electrified NH₃ plants would be around 26-27 GJ/tonne NH₃ [11]. However, an ASU is still required, which is very expensive and not easy to down-scale to smaller plant sizes (for distributed generation).

Figure 4. High-level block diagrams of different methods for producing ammonia: (A) conventional approach: steam reforming of natural gas, with air added to the secondary reformer, (B) combination of alkaline electrolysis and cryogenic air separation, (C) combination of SOEC and cryogenic air separation, and (D) a new method where SOEC provides both H₂ and N₂. In (D), SOEC acts simultaneously as an air separation unit and an electrolysis unit. Note that part of the heat required to convert water into steam can be provided by heat from the Haber-Bosch reactor.

Haldor Topsoe has developed a new process for ammonia synthesis gas generation that utilizes the unique capabilities of SOEC acting as an oxygen separation membrane, thereby obviating the need for an ASU (Fig. 4D) [11,15]. In such a plant, multiple steam electrolysis units would be connected in series, with catalytic burners located between consecutive stacks. Feed gas for the Haber-Bosch reaction (H₂ : N₂ = 3:1) would be generated on the fuel-side of the SOEC by combusting some of the electrolytic H₂ with air, which is added to the gas stream in the catalytic burners between stacks [11,15]. A 50 kW electrified ammonia plant based on the design shown in Fig. 4D will be demonstrated in

the project “SOC4NH3”, funded by the Danish Energy Agency. The project partners include Haldor Topsoe (coordinator, technology and stack supplier), Aarhus University (host for the demonstration plant), DTU Energy (cell and stack tests). Additionally, transmission system operator Energinet, wind turbine manufacturer Vestas, and energy companies Ørsted and Equinor are to supply knowhow for techno- and socio-economic evaluations. The project will also include cell- and stack-level testing of NH₃ as fuel for SOFC.

Haldor Topsoe has been selected as the technology and catalyst provider for the ammonia synthesis section of the world’s largest green ammonia plant, to be commissioned in 2025 [14]. The 5 billion USD project, owned by Air Products, NEOM and ACWA Power, will use 4 GW of renewable power to generate 650 t of H₂ per day, converting it to 1.2 million t of NH₃ per year [14]. The project will boast the world’s largest ammonia loop. The produced ammonia will be distributed globally and cracked back to carbon-free H₂ for use at hydrogen refueling stations (Fig. 5). The project is an important milestone in Haldor Topsoe’s NH₃ electrification roadmap [6]. While this plant will be based on alkaline electrolyzers, we envision that green NH₃ plants based on SOEC technology will be built in the future.

Figure 5. A high-level block diagram of the NH₃ plant powered by 4 GW of renewables, along with the proposed use of NH₃ for green mobility. Adapted from [14].

Conclusions

Haldor Topsoe is commercializing SOEC technology for CO production (eCOsTM), with two electrolysis plants (each with a capacity of 96 Nm³/h CO) scheduled for commissioning later this year. The plants will be the first subsidy-free SOEC plants in the world.

The proprietary TSP-1 stack design is suitable for long-term operation in dry CO₂ electrolysis. System tests have demonstrated stack lifetimes of almost 14 000 h (corresponding to ~30 000 Nm³ (35.5 tonnes) of CO produced per stack), as well as robustness towards thermal and load cycles. The degradation rate for the stack was 7.9 mV kh⁻¹ per cell, the average power consumption was 3.44 kWh/Nm³ CO, and the Faradaic efficiency remained between 99-100% throughout the test. Based on these performance metrics, SOEC is by far the most efficient and mature technology for electrochemical CO₂ reduction.

Haldor Topsoe's activities in H₂O electrolysis include continued development of an SOEC demonstration unit for biogas upgrading, aimed at lifting the TRL of the technology from 6 to 8. A new concept for producing feed gas for ammonia synthesis using SOECs, and without the need for cryogenic air separation units, will be demonstrated in a recently awarded project by the Danish Energy Agency.

Haldor Topsoe has been selected as the technology and catalyst provider for the ammonia synthesis section of the world's largest green ammonia plant, to be commissioned in 2025. The project is an important milestone in Topsoe's NH₃ electrification roadmap, and it is envisioned that green NH₃ plants based on SOEC technology will be built in the future.

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